

INTEGRATED HYBRID CERAMIC/S2-GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITE ARMOUR

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ABSTRACT

Armour systems which incorporate conventional ceramic strike plates may experience radial cracking after first ballistic impact, leading to a degraded multi-hit performance. Polymer/ceramic armour systems have been shown to be a promising solution for this problem. This study evaluated the ballistic performance of a range of polymer ceramic armour systems. The main comparison was made between using a polymer ceramic strike face and embedding the ceramic powder within a polymer matrix fibre reinforced (FRP) composite. Here, Boron Carbide (B₄C) powder was embedded within multiple layers of S2-Glass fabric, which together were infused with a phenolic resin to form an integrated hybrid ceramic/FRP composite armour. Four configurations were studied including the FRP composite with no ceramic content and three hybrid configurations where 25 wt.% of the composite was replaced with the polymer ceramic. The ballistic performance of the developed armour systems was evaluated against FMJ M80 NATO Ball 7.62×51 mm calibre projectiles. The integration of ceramic powder in between multiple layers of fabric improved the ballistic V₅₀ by up to 14% for the first projectile impact and by up to 20 % for the subsequent projectile impact compared to the case where the entire ceramic powder was placed at the strike face. In addition, radial cracking was eliminated in the integrated system by avoiding a bulk ceramic layer. However, there was no improvement compared to the FRP composite with no ceramic, suggesting optimisation of the ceramic material and powder size are necessary for any future development. Damage mechanisms and failure modes were analysed for the studied targets, showing a two stage perforation process, with a transition plane similar to those previously identified for thick composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Armour systems for protection of personnel and land vehicles against various ballistic threats often employ ceramics as part of the strike plate. Bonded to a backing layer, the ceramic layer breaks up or deforms the penetrator by fracture and erosion, while the remnant is caught by the backing layer [1]. The brittle nature of the ceramic strike plates cause radial cracking in the ceramic and debonding of the ceramic layer from the backing material, consequently degrading the ballistic performance of the armour system when subjected to multiple impacts within the damaged zone [2].

One method used by designers to overcome the radial cracking issue is through the use of modular ceramic tiles, where crack propagation stops at the edges of the tile [3]. However, these provide reduced performance if impacts occur near the edge of the tile. This shortcoming was confirmed by a recent numerical study on various bioinspired modular ceramic tiles with steel backing, where the ballistic performance of the monolithic ceramic was found to be superior to the modular designs evaluated in that study [4]. The disintegration of ceramic upon impact at the weak areas near the joints demands for thicker tiles or overlapping edges (e.g. 45° tapering of tiles) as mitigation strategies [3]. However, a monolithic ceramic strike face was proven to be superior compared to the proposed

solutions [3]. For body armour, an intermediate solution is to wrap the ceramic with a thin layer of FRP composite which reduces the pulverizing of the ceramic and increases the projectile erosion [3].

In another recent effort to address the issue of radial cracking in body armour systems, the sintered ceramic strike face was replaced with a polymer ceramic strike face [5]. These polymer ceramic composites utilised an aramid backing material and were shown to be effective in deforming projectiles across a range of projectile calibres [5]. In addition, this armour configuration showed significantly less cracking than a monolithic B₄C tile of equivalent areal density. This suggests that this design methodology represents a promising strategy to tackle the radial cracking issue. However, it should be noted that no single or multi-hit V₅₀ comparison was made between the polymer ceramic composite and a monolithic B₄C strike face armour. An alternative approach for improving the performance of body armours using a polymer ceramic composite was evaluated in [6]. In this case the ceramic particles were sprayed onto the aramid fibre reinforcement layers to enhance the protection against knife threats. The optimum mass fraction of 20 wt.% of the SiC particles, achieved the same performance in terms of knife penetration depth with a 10% reduction in mass, when compared to the baseline aramid composite without embedded SiC particles [6].

This investigation is aimed at utilising the concept of a polymer ceramic composite armour by directly comparing the ballistic performance of an armour system using a polymer ceramic strike face with a fibre reinforced composite backing to armour systems using ceramic particles embedded into a fibre reinforced composite. The intended application for these systems would be for vehicle protection or body armour. The ballistic performance of these systems was evaluated using both a single hit V₅₀ test methodology as well as an analysis of multi-hit performance. In addition, the polymer ceramic composites are directly compared to a fibre reinforced composite of equivalent areal density, which is considered to be the control case for this investigation.

2 MATERIALS AND MANUFACTURING

The fibre reinforced composite was made using glass fibre and phenolic resin. S2-Glass was selected as it has been the subject of extensive experimental and modelling studies in the last three decades because of its potential as a monolithic ballistic protection armour in military vehicles [7-10] or as a backing layer in various ceramic composite armour configurations [11-13]. Plain weave S2-Glass™ (AGY Holding Corp.) fabric and Hexion Durite SC-1008™ phenolic resin were used as the fibre reinforcement and matrix, respectively. B₄C powder was used as the ceramic inclusion due to its use in body armour systems [5]. Fabrics with the stacking sequence of [0]_n were infused using a vacuum assisted resin infusion technique for the samples used in the control group.

Four armour configurations were fabricated including; the control group, which was made using 110 layers of S2-Glass fabric, and three hybrid armour configurations, where 25% of the fabric weight was replaced with an equivalent weight of B₄C powder (Fig. 1). For the type I hybrid, the entire mass of ceramic powder was spread across the top of 82 layers of fabric. For the type II hybrid, the ceramic powder was dispersed between the top 25% of fabric on top of the remaining 62 layers of fabrics. In the type III hybrid, ceramic powder was dispersed between the top 50% of fabric on top of the remaining 42 layers of fabric. For both the type II and III hybrid samples, the ceramic powder was evenly spread out between every second layer of fabric. Samples were then prepared using the vacuum assisted resin infusion technique described for the control group. The manufactured average sample thicknesses and areal densities are presented in Table 1. Specimens were cut from 330 mm × 330 mm panels to the final dimensions of 150 mm × 150 mm.

Fig.1. Schematic of the three hybrid fibre reinforced composite/ceramic integrated armour systems.

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Ballistic V_{50} tests were conducted following the MIL-STD-662F-December 1997 standard [14]. Samples were fixed to a stationary frame using four G-clamps on four corners of each sample. The projectile used in all tests was the FMJ M80 NATO Ball, 7.62×51 mm calibre. After obtaining the 6-shot V_{50} for each configuration as per the standard, a second shot was conducted for the base composite and three hybrid configurations to provide an indication of their potential multi-hit performance. The second shot was performed on 4 to 5 specimens per configuration. A second shot V_{50} was then determined based on these additional tests. The location of first and second impact points are shown in Figure 2.

Fig.2. Schematic of projectile impact locations on composite/ceramic integrated armour targets.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Ballistic Performance

Table 1 shows the average areal density, average thickness, ballistic V_{50} , and percent change of V_{50} for control and three hybrid configurations. A comparison between the three hybrid configurations provides valuable design information for polymer ceramic armour systems. The type II and III hybrid systems outperformed the type I hybrid system in terms of both the single shot and double shot V_{50} . In the single-impact test, the type II and III hybrids recorded a 14% and 12% higher V_{50} compared to the type I hybrid, respectively. The relative performance was further increased for the second shot to 20% and 15% higher V_{50} for type II and type III hybrids, respectively. Further experiments are necessary to determine if this positive trend continues after subsequent impacts. These results highlight that for this mass fraction of ceramic, superior ballistic performance is provided by embedding the ceramic into the FRP rather than using a polymer ceramic strike face. Additionally, as the type II hybrid marginally outperformed the type III hybrid, for polymer ceramic armour system with embedded ceramics it may be advantageous to provide a higher distribution of the ceramic particles closer to the front face of the armour panel.

In both single and double impact scenarios, the base S2-Glass/SC-1008 composite (i.e. control) showed the highest ballistic V_{50} . It is concluded that replacing S2-Glass fabric with an equivalent weight of B_4C powder does not significantly improve the ballistic performance of the protective system. Based on the comparative study for different ceramic particle sizes in [5], it is envisaged that the fine microstructure of the ceramic powder and its non-optimised properties are the reason for the lack of a significant improvement compared to the control FRP composite. A combination of ceramic powders with different materials or different particle sizes, e.g. as developed in [5], might potentially improve the ballistic performance of the integrated ceramic/FRP composite compared to the control.

Table 1. Summary of V_{50} ballistic test results for composite and hybrid composite/ceramic armours.

Sample	B ₄ C Location (% weight)	Test	Areal Density (kg/m ²)	Thickness (mm)	V ₅₀ (m/s)	V ₅₀ % change vs. Control	V ₅₀ % change vs. Hybrid I
Control	(0)	1 st Impact	53.1	27.1	751	N/A	N/A
Hybrid I	Impact Face (25)	1 st Impact	49.3	27.8	648	-13.7	N/A
Hybrid II	Distributed in top 25% of thickness (25)	1 st Impact	51.3	28.6	740	-1.5	+14.2
Hybrid III	Distributed in top 50% of thickness (25)	1 st Impact	51.2	27.6	724	-3.6	+11.7
Control	(0)	2 nd Impact	53.1	27.1	727	N/A	N/A
Hybrid I	Impact Face (25)	2 nd Impact	49.3	27.8	595	-18.2	N/A
Hybrid II	Distributed in top 25% of thickness (25)	2 nd Impact	51.3	28.6	713	-1.9	+19.8
Hybrid III	Distributed in top 50% of thickness (25)	2 nd Impact	51.2	27.6	684	-5.9	+15.0

4.2 Damage Mechanisms

Figures 3 to 6 present the photographs of representative specimens from all configurations after first impact. Photographs are provided of both the front and back faces. The damage induced in the type II and type III hybrids were similar to the control. Two separate stages of perforation were observed which are well described for thick UHMWPE composite targets in [15]. A transition plane separates these two stages and their associated failure mechanisms. In stage one, fibre breakage and shearing are the main failure mechanisms which resulted in a localised damage zone around the impact point. In addition, few delamination planes are present at stage one area which were caused by the shock induced rarefaction. In stage two, multiple delamination planes are present between the transition plane and the back face of the target. These delaminations were caused by the sub-laminate bulging and material drawing.

Whilst stage two of perforation for the hybrid case I was similar to the other three cases in terms of failure mechanisms, the stage one perforation has an additional initial perforation step. This initial perforation step is contained within the polymer ceramic layer at the strike face. A large conical damage zone was observed at the strike face which is a typical of ceramic armours. Radial cracks start from the edge of the conical damage zone and extend to the free edges of the targets where additional material loss was observed. This additional material loss was due to the discontinuity at the edges of the target and is not expected to occur in larger targets. The density of the radial cracks were much lower than the observations for conventional ceramics backed by an S2-Glass FRP composite [16].

Figures 7 to 10 show the images of representative specimens from all configurations following the second impact. For the control, type II and type III hybrids, the perforation mechanism for the second impact was similar to the two stage perforation of the first impact. In stage one of perforation, the damage zone at the target strike face around the second impact point remained localised with no observable overlap with the first impact. However, there was a significant overlap between the two impacts within the stage two damage area. This resulted in more extensive delamination and fibre rupture, leading to a lower V_{50} for the second impact. For the type I hybrid, the stage one perforation showed significant overlap in the polymer ceramic area, where the damaged area was larger than the summation of two conical damage zones, leading to a significantly larger exposed area of the backing material. These observations show the advantages of the type II and III hybrid armours compared to the type I hybrid armour. Further non-destructive evaluation of samples is required to characterise the damage inside the targets and to develop a more comprehensive understanding of the damage mechanisms.

Fig.3. A representative sample from control group after single impact at velocity of 744 m/s resulting in a complete penetration. (a) and (b) show front and back faces.

Fig.4. A representative sample from hybrid I group after single impact at velocity of 648 m/s resulting in a partial penetration. (a) and (b) show front and back faces.

Fig.5. A representative sample from hybrid II group after single impact at velocity of 736 m/s resulting in a partial penetration. (a) and (b) show front and back faces.

Fig.6. A representative sample from hybrid III group after single impact at velocity of 720 m/s resulting in a partial penetration. (a) and (b) show front and back faces.

Fig.7. A representative sample from control group after two impacts at velocities of 778 m/s (complete penetration) and 713 m/s (partial penetration). (a) and (b) show front and back faces.

Fig.8. A representative sample from hybrid I group after two impacts at velocities of 656 m/s (complete penetration) and 591 m/s (partial penetration). (a) and (b) show front and back faces.

Fig.9. A representative sample from hybrid II group after two impacts at velocities of 766 m/s (complete penetration) and 714 m/s (complete penetration). (a) and (b) show front and back faces.

Fig.10. A representative sample from hybrid III group after two impacts at velocities of 718 m/s (complete penetration) and 702 m/s (complete penetration). (a) and (b) show front and back faces.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this investigation the ballistic performance of a range of integrated hybrid ceramic/FRP composite armours was experimentally evaluated. The integration of ceramic powder in between multiple layers of the FRP composite was found to improve the ballistic performance of the armour compared to the monolithic polymer ceramic with FRP backing. The integration of ceramic powder in between multiple layers of fabric improved the ballistic V_{50} by up to 14% for the first projectile impact and by up to 20% for the second projectile impact compared to the case where entire ceramic powder was placed at the strike face. In addition, radial cracking was eliminated. However, there was no improvement compared to the baseline FRP composite with no ceramic, suggesting optimisation of the ceramic material and grain size are necessary for any future development. The damage mechanisms and failure modes were analysed for the studied targets and a two stage perforation process was identified. A transition plane was observed between the two stages of penetration which has been previously identified for thick composite targets. Another advantage of the proposed integrated armour system is the flexibility of the manufacturing method in terms of the armour geometry (e.g. curvature), potentially making it a suitable method for fabrication of body armour or vehicle components with complex geometries.

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REFERENCES

- [1] W. A. Gooch, "An overview of ceramic armor applications," in *6th Technical Conference IDEE*, Trencin, Slovakia, 2004.
- [2] E. Medvedovski, "Lightweight ceramic composite armour system," *Advances in Applied Ceramics*, vol. 105, no. 5, pp. 241-245, 2006/10/01 2006.
- [3] E. Medvedovski, "Ballistic performance of armour ceramics: Influence of design and structure. Part 2," *Ceramics International*, vol. 36, no. 7, pp. 2117-2127, 2010/09/01/ 2010.
- [4] V. González-Albuixech, M. Rodríguez-Millán, T. Ito, J. Loya, and M. Miguélez, "Numerical analysis for design of bioinspired ceramic modular armors for ballistic protections," *International Journal of Damage Mechanics*, vol. 0, no. 0, p. 1056789518795203, 2018.
- [5] M. Naebe, J. Sandlin, I. Crouch, and B. Fox, "Novel polymer-ceramic composites for protection against ballistic fragments," *Polymer Composites*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 180-186, 2013.
- [6] W. Rubin *et al.*, "Enhancing stab resistance of thermoset-aramid composite fabrics by coating with SiC particles," *Journal of Industrial Textiles*, vol. 48, no. 7, pp. 1228-1241, 2019.
- [7] S.-C. Chou and E. DeLuca, "Dynamic response of S-2 glass reinforced plastic structural armor," ARMY RESEARCH LAB WATERTOWN MA MATERIALS DIRECTORATE 1993.
- [8] B. Z. Haque, J. L. Harrington, and J. W. Gillespie, "Multi-hit ballistic impact on S-2 glass/SC15 thick-section composites: experiments," *The Journal of Strain Analysis for Engineering Design*, vol. 47, no. 7, pp. 480-494, 2012.
- [9] M. V. Hosur, M. R. Karim, and S. Jeelani, "Studies on Stitched Woven S2 Glass/Epoxy Laminates under Low Velocity and Ballistic Impact Loading," *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, vol. 23, no. 12, pp. 1313-1323, 2004.
- [10] C. T. Key and C. Scott Alexander, "Experimental Testing and Numerical Modeling of Ballistic Impact on S-2 Glass/SC15 Composites," *Journal of Dynamic Behavior of Materials*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 373-386, 2018/09/01 2018.
- [11] A. Haque, A. Abutalib, K. Rahul, U. Vaidya, H. Mahfuz, and S. Jeelani, "Ballistic Performance of Monolithic Ceramic Backed by S2-Glass/Vinyl Ester Composites," *Center for Advanced Materials, Tuskegee University, Tuskegee, Alabama-36088, USA*, 1998.

- [12] H. Mahfuz *et al.*, "Investigation of high-velocity impact on integral armor using finite element method," *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 203-217, 2000/02/01/ 2000.
- [13] H. Mahfuz, Y. Zhu, A. Haque, U. Vaidya, and S. Jeelani, "Response of Integral Armor Under High Velocity Impact An Experimental and Finite Element Study," in *12th International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM-12), Palais Des Congress, Paris*, 1999.
- [14] *Military Standard, V50 Ballistic Test for Armor, MIL-STD-662F*, 1997.
- [15] L. H. Nguyen, S. Ryan, S. J. Cimpoeu, A. P. Mouritz, and A. C. Orifici, "The effect of target thickness on the ballistic performance of ultra high molecular weight polyethylene composite," *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, vol. 75, pp. 174-183, 2015/01/01/ 2015.
- [16] K. Dateraksa, K. Sujirote, R. McCUISTON, and D. Atong, "Ballistic performance of ceramic/S 2-glass composite armor," *Journal of Metals, Materials and Minerals*, vol. 22, no. 2, 2012.